

The five-year visioning activity included considering three aspects of open and FAIR data sharing. This activity helped to establish a positive tone for the evening discussion at dinner and the work to come on the second day.

Five-year vision of:

- 1) Make depositing open and FAIR data a priority for all
- 2) Societies recognize and incentivize FAIR data practices
- 3) Global infrastructure to support FAIR data and tools

1) Make depositing open and FAIR data a priority for all

- Five-year (2025) vision includes:
 - Coordinated recognition that data sharing is a good / priority, but also recognition that one size does not fit all.
 - Broad and coordinated education of research community, both direct and indirect from a diversity of sources.
 - Authors have data in format easy to share and make authors aware that they don't need to make public immediately.
 - Reviewers start requesting to see the data.
 - Stakeholders researched and highlighted positive impact of data sharing. Showed (and provided tools) to make sharing easy and improve research efficiency.
 - FAIR data toolkit and primer made widely available by funders, institutions, publishers that made clear the benefit and ease of data sharing.
 - Policies in place for publishers sign on and push authors to do it and tell authors condition of publication.
 - A lot of education from publishers and societies.
 - Made it easy and not burdensome
 - Targeted young scientist,
 - Tenure changed to include well-preserved/shared datasets
 - Orientation at universities and include data management for grad students; Citation management, scholarly comms
 - Worked with Science libraries

- Demonstrated contributions in meaningful way that a person was a key part of project team and is associated
- We made life easier to the researcher and efficient
- Science population transition
- Measure and articulate the value of data
- Panels care at the award stage.
- Industry collaborators need your data
- How did we make this work?
 - Stakeholders (University Presidents, societies, funders, publishers) MOVED in mass to influence researchers
 - Funders require data management plans (DMP); this policy is enforced or actionable and the DMPs are assessed. Be transparent about what you did.
Funders mandate data deposit
- Tool kit needs.
 - Embargo details in FAQ
 - Share ways to deposit data that is not public
 - More digestible training - Develop and make widely available basic
 - Style guide
 - Reach people where they are
 - Graduate training
 - Empower young professionals by educating, skill building (credit for their work, more marketable - especially in sectors beyond academy)
- What society supports made this happen?

- PEER Pressure for PIs to start teaching data sharing
- Leveled playing field across differently sized institutions
- Harness self-interest: research ethics, research integrity, need for transparency in the face of increased skepticism of research / retractions, rewards/recognition for data sharing / curation / tagging.
- Where were potential disconnects, roadblocks and points of failure?
 - Shopping around publications to avoid deposit or data policies they don't like, if not consistent
 - Personal standards can vary
 - Did not know what's in it for them. Value proposition
 - Burdensome
 - Sharing of knowledge by PIs not feasible for post-docs and graduate students who commonly do the work. PIs don't have the knowledge to share.

2) Societies recognize and incentivize FAIR data practices

- Five-year (2025) vision includes:
 - Individual societies can share consistent definitions of “data”
 - Framing these definitions through best practices and principles
 - There is a fundamental culture change needed
 - We addressed “Why should I change my practices now?”
 - Technological advances make this possible now
 - Many publishers modifying policies to include FAIR data elements at once would be powerful and useful for creating change
- How did we get there?
 - Policies may roll out in phases; availability statements, required repos, no supplements, etc.
 - Societies publicize data and repository definitions and options
 - Societies determine where in the organization we solve the data problems. Combining data science/management with outreach and project management.
 - Conduct pilot: Editors to submit data with all of their publications
 - Authors recognized/badged for including data that is FAIR
 - This will take 6+ months, but the champions will drive adoption
 - Encouragement of bottom-up, community pressure to effectively to create organizational change
 - Frame value for the individual researcher as a vital element

- Reassure researchers that the work for providing FAIR data is manageable and there are resources to support them would help them change their practices
- Gather and promote success stories!
- Provide a “Data Counselor” to assist and reassure researchers
- Promote the value of participating vs details of how to participate
- Value propositions that convince researchers to participate, must be combined with making it easy will work. Easy TOOLS.
- Rapid researcher behavior change requires the use of the “stick” such as funder and publisher policies. Ensure there as many incentives as possible that have meaning to the researcher so that the behavior change is more likely to be sustainable.
- Where were potential disconnects, roadblocks and points of failure?
 - Researchers are not incentivized to publish their datasets along with their papers
 - Researchers aren’t assured that even their responsibly managed and deposited data will be accessed
 - “Why would I do something that might allow me to be proven wrong?”
 - Have to get past the barriers of it is too hard; researchers may still push back
 - Repositories are much more hands on now, but are not funded for this role. Need to address this disconnect.
 - Need to determine who “owns” repositories, which are so important to this process? How do we ensure that they will support the role of persistence of the scientific record?

3) Global infrastructure to support FAIR data and tools

- Five-year (2025) vision includes:
 - The infrastructure for open and FAIR data sharing is satisfactory, though could still use improvements.
- How did we get there?
 - Repository Finder Tool works for locating the appropriate repository.
 - A road map to becoming a certified repository is developed and valued by societies and researchers.
 - We solved the problem about linking publication metadata with dataset metadata.
 - We solved the problem with citing the right level of granularity of the dataset.
 - We have clearly determined preferred repositories that help researchers.
 - We have robust guidance for reviewers concerning data.
 - Repositories (with support from community) has determined how to conduct peer review on datasets as part of the research lifecycle.
- Where were potential disconnects, roadblocks and points of failure?
 - Becoming a trusted repository is difficult (e.g. CoreTrustSeal).
 - Determining the right level of granularity citation is still unclear.
 - Peer review of data requires an understanding of the science. Very difficult for repository to conduct, or for the journal to conduct.